

Crypto-currency Price Prediction Using Machine Learning(AutoTS)

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Abstract - Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies are becoming increasingly popular among investors. It is investigated in the proposed work how to accurately anticipate the Bitcoin price by taking into account several criteria that influence the Bitcoin price. This research first identifies the price trends on day-to-day variations in the Bitcoin price, as well as providing information on Bitcoin price patterns. The dataset includes open, high volume, closely adjusted, low, and the close price details for Bitcoin value up to the present day. The main objective of this research is to predict and estimate the future bitcoin price, as well as daily returns and profits that can be made by investing in bitcoin.

Keywords : Prediction, cryptocurrency, AutoTS, pandas.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cryptocurrencies are digital assets that people invest in and use to make purchases online. Bitcoin is currently one of the best Cryptocurrency. Bitcoin is used for automated investments all over the world. Bitcoin is decentralised in the means that no single person or entity owns it.. Bitcoin transactions are straightforward since they are not controlled by any country. Different business hubs known as bitcoin trades are available for investment.

These allow people to trade Bitcoins in a variety of currencies. Mt. Gox is the largest Bitcoin market in the world, keeping bitcoin like a digital bank. The timestamp information handled in this market, as well as the record of a large number of exchanges, is referred to as Blockchain. Every piece of blockchain data is encrypted. Only the wallet ID is made public, as a result, deals made in the client's name remain confidential.

Bitcoin is a successful digital currency that was brought into the financial industry dependent on its one-of-a-kind protocol and structure created by Satoshi Nakamoto [7]. Bitcoin is a crypto-currency that aims to decentralise the money market. Investors in the Bitcoin market form trust ties through the development of Blockchain and the application of cryptography methods. As a result of breakthroughs in Blockchain and machine learning, Bitcoin is growing popularity these days.

The highly volatile nature of the crypto-currency market has a considerable impact on exchange procedures. Bitcoin, the most popular crypto-currency, is nonetheless plagued by volatility. As a result, major research efforts are required to

develop an efficient method of crypto-currency price prediction using machine learning techniques.

This proposed paper focuses on prediction and forecasting of bitcoin prices which is done by using AutoTS. AutoTS is a component of AutoML that automates some of the machine learning pipeline's components. It will train numerous time series models with a single line of code, allowing the user to choose the best one for the problem statement. Along with AutoTS pandas package is also used for analysing the dataset containing historical data of Bitcoin price.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Inamedar et al. [1] specifies RNN with LSTM or LSTM network alone is used for sentiment analysis. Short patterns can be remembered by an RNN network. Extended short-term memory (LSTM) has the ability to remember lengthy sequences of data, making it ideal for lengthy strings such as Twitter data and news data. After completing sentiment analysis on Twitter, news data and mapping it with prior values, Random Forest correctly forecasts the value of Bitcoin for the following two days. Historic data has been discovered to have the most weight among the four criteria, followed by the volume of Bitcoin exchanged. The value of news and Twitter sentiment scores is emphasized. The fact that tweets and news feed scores are mostly impartial is one of the reasons why they have minimal impact. The prediction on two days are the output characteristic of MAE and RMSE is the same, hence the unit of both mistakes is dollars. Prices on day one can range from \$13.0733 to \$15.1686, while prices on day two can range from \$13.0733 to \$15.1686.

Rathan et al. [2] used Bitcoin dataset in this study, which spans from 2011 to the present day, and ML models such as Decision Tree and Linear Regression are used. One of the most common learning models used in classifications is the decision tree. The dataset into two or more sets using this technique are partitioned. Internal nodes in the decision tree represent a feature test, a branch represents the result, and leaf's represent decisions made after further processing. Linear Regression is a supervised Machine Learning model that finds the best fit linear line between the independent and

dependent variables, or the linear link between them. Decision Tree and Linear regression models are also used to estimate prices for the next five days. Here performance of both algorithms are compared and linear regression outperforms Decision tree.

Roy et al. [3] uses AR, MA, and ARIMA models to forecast bitcoin prices for the following 10 days. The AR in ARIMA stands for regressing the evolving variable of interest on its own lagged (i.e., prior) values. The regression error is a linear combination of error factors whose values occurred simultaneously and at different times in the past, as indicated by the MA part of the equation. Following the research, we determined that the MA model has the lowest accuracy (87.58%), while the ARIMA model has a higher accuracy (90.31%).

McNally et al. [4] objectives of this paper was to see how effective it was to predict the direction of Bitcoin's price in US dollars. The pricing data came from the Bitcoin Price Index. The job is performed with varying degrees of success using a Bayesian Optimised RNN and a LSTM network. The LSTM is the most accurate, with an accuracy of 52% and an RMSE of 8%. The well-known ARIMA model for time series prediction is used as a contrast to deep learning methods. The ARIMA forecast, which has a poor track record, is outperformed by the non-linear deep learning methods, as expected.

Tandon et al. [5] research presents a model for predicting the price of the Bitcoin using different neural network methodologies, such as RNN and LSTM, as well as 10-fold cross validation. This research looks at various trends in the Bitcoin market, as well as learning about important aspects that can be used to anticipate price. The daily price figure is estimated using neural network models. This study employs new activation functions in order to increase efficiency. The proposed model is also compared to other current models in the same domain, such as RNN with LSTM, Linear Regression, and Random Forest in this research. The data for this study was acquired from the website "coinmarket."

HO et al. [6] study uses network analysis and centrality indicators on the daily close price of the top 120 cryptocurrencies to look at the evolution of the cryptocurrency industry between 2013 and 2020. Major finding of this research was - From 2013 to 2016, the overall cross-return connection across cryptocurrencies weakened before increasing again;- Until mid-2016, cryptocurrencies primarily used for payment, such as Bitcoin, dominated the market, followed by those designed for blockchain-based applications, particularly data storage and recording, such as MAID and FCT, between mid-2016 and mid-2017. Due to its prevailing smart contract capacity, which can automate the execution of business tasks stated in contracts, ETH has replaced BTC as the benchmark cryptocurrency, along with its strongly related cryptocurrencies such as ADA, NEO, and OMG. Furthermore, QTUM and BNB have partially superseded ETH to assume the primary positions as a result of their large community participation during the COVID-19 pandemic: - The use of centrality measurements can help increase the accuracy of short-term bitcoin price forecast.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this proposed paper predicting and forecasting the Bitcoin prices of future and find daily returns and profits that can be made from Bitcoin investment are focused. Steps involved in this anticipated work are :

- data collection and visualisation
- prediction and forecasting using AutoTS
- finding returns and profits

Requirements for implementation of this work are:

- Dataset (In the form of csv file)
- GitHub
- Google Colab

A. Data Collection and Visualisation

The price Prediction model forecasts the price considering historical price data. The historical price data is taken from yahoo. The data features include Open- price of cryptocurrency when market opens, Close- price of cryptocurrency when market Closes (price adjusted for splits), High- highest listed price of the day, Low- lowest listed price of the day, Adjacent close – close price adjusted for splits and dividend and/or capital gain distribution, Volume-number of cryptocurrency has traded over a period, Date. Null values are removed using dropna() function.

Figure 1. Visualizing the datas

B. Prediction and Forecasting using AutoTS

For predicting values, at first define the model and pass the parameters. Parameters are frequency, ensemble, drop_data, forecast-length then model is created using AutoTS() function. After the model is created it is fitted using fit() according to dataset, parameters in fit() data, value_col='Close', id_col=None, date_col='Date', . The prediction and forecasting is done using model.predict() and predict.forecast(). Forecast-length determine the number of days upto which forecasting of cryptocurrency price.

Figure 2. forecasting Bitcoin prices using AutoTS

Figure 4. returns from forecasted price

C. Finding returns and profits

After prediction and forecasting of bitcoin prices, from the forecasted prices using pct_change() the returns are predicted. Formula:

$$\text{predicted_returns} = \text{forecast}['\text{Close}']. \text{pct_change}()$$

From the predicted returns profits can be calculated by using Formula:

$$\text{Profit} = \text{predicted_returns} * \text{budget}$$

Figure 3. Process of predicting and finding returns, profits

2022-05-26	0.297464
2022-05-27	-1.163689
2022-05-28	0.370073
2022-05-29	-2.843874
2022-05-30	-9.078962
2022-05-31	-9.973125
2022-06-01	-7.873121
2022-06-02	-6.891230
2022-06-03	-6.764315

Figure 5. Estimated Profits

IV. CONCLUSION

Bitcoin is a flourishing crypto-currency market, and several economics and price prediction studies have been conducted. In this proposed work Bitcoin dataset containing historical price data from 2017 to 2022 are considered. Here by using AutoTS model bitcoin price up to next 25 days can be forecasted.

Prices can be more precisely forecasted for extended periods of time in the future by taking into account other properties such as blockchain features etc.

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